

TRAUMATIC ORAL MUCOSAL LESIONS IN PATIENTS WITH HEART FAILURE

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Abstract. *Cardiovascular diseases (CVD) are the leading cause of death in many countries. Given the multifactorial etiology of CVDs, the close conjugation of risk factors (FRs) with each other and their mutually reinforcing effects, their impact on health is considered in combination rather than individually. Constant nibbling of cheeks and lips may be a bad habit caused by stress. Sometimes this repetitive behavior can be one of the symptoms of obsessive-compulsive disorder.*

In addition, problems with the bite often arise due to diseases of the temporomandibular joint and bite pathologies. Also, a person can traumatize the mucosa with a filling or sharp edge of the tooth, if it is located outside the dental arch or its wells are excessively sharp due to individual anatomical features. There are cases of asymptomatic disease. With a strong, aggressive bite, complaints of pain, burning in the mucous membrane and sometimes swelling appear. Since the mucous membrane is constantly provided with mechanical irritation, the production of more keratin in the epithelium is stimulated.

Keywords: *cardiovascular system, Injuries from food, drinks, cigarettes, Chemical burns, Orthodontic and orthopedic treatment injuries, oral mucosa (OM).*

There are cases of asymptomatic course of the disease. With a disease of the cardiovascular system, the patient has complaints of pain, burning in the mucous membrane and sometimes swelling. Since the mucous membrane constantly receives mechanical irritation, the production of more keratin in the epithelium is stimulated.

The affected area thickens, changes color - becomes white. As a rule, the lesion is uneven, with irregular edges. Affected areas are often located symmetrically, for example, on the mucous membrane of the cheeks on the right and left sides, along the line of bowing of the teeth. With a long bite and poor hygiene, bacteria (mainly staphylococci, streptococci) or, less often, fungi of the genus *Candida* join the lesion. That is, bacterial traumatic wounds are frequent complications.

Pathologic changes of oral mucosa in cardiovascular diseases in accordance with the above data are found in 40-80 % of patients. However, like other general diseases of the body, cardiovascular diseases do not cause changes that are characteristic only for this group of patients. Changes in the SOPR in cardiovascular diseases in a significant way to a great extent depend on the degree of insufficiency of blood imagination, the state of the vascular wall.

In cardiovascular insufficiency accompanied by circulatory failure, there is general puffiness, cyanosis of oral mucosa and red lip border. Such condition may be combined with dryness of the OM and its edema, as a result of which the tongue increases in size, and teeth imprints appear on the OM neck and tongue.

Occurrence of trophic changes in the OM, up to ulcers formation. Trophic ulcers are localized mainly in the posterior part of the oral cavity, on the mucosa of the cheeks, alveolar process, on the tongue, on the mucosa of the retromolar area and other areas. Ulcers come in

various sizes (2-5 mm and larger). They are covered with pale gray plaque with a malodorous odor, sharply painful when touching and eating. The absence of inflammatory reaction in the surrounding tissues is characteristic. Ulcers localized on the mucosa of the alveolar process can spread to the mucosa of the cheek, lip, cause partial necrosis of the alveolar bone and jaw. Due to necrotic decay, severe bleeding may occur.

One of the complications during orthopedic treatment is prosthetic stomatitis. It mostly occurs in people over 60 years of age. At this age, many people suffer from dry mouth syndrome. Therefore, the treatment of traumatic stomatitis should be combined with measures aimed at improving salivation.

Symptoms of traumatic denture stomatitis: pain (moderate or severe);
the presence of a lesion (erosion or ulcerative-erosive lesions);
hyperemia (redness - from pink to bright red);
swelling (can be absent, small or obvious).

Chemical burns. In the event of an incident - poisoning with household chemicals, consumption of acids or alkaline substances, acute pain immediately appears in the mucous membrane of the oral cavity. When large amounts of chemicals enter the oral cavity, swallowing function is almost always impaired and breathing may be difficult. Such an emergency requires immediate hospitalization and treatment at a burn center.

When the mucosa is exposed to acid, tissue necrosis is not as deep as when damaged by alkali. The severity of the damage depends on the chemical concentration, its size and the duration of exposure to the mucous membrane.

Chemical burns of the gums can occur during teeth whitening at home or at the dentist's office. This happens especially often when using gel based on high concentration of hydrogen peroxide. A bleaching burn looks like a limited area of gray mucosal necrosis. The pain is clearly expressed.

Thermal injuries from food, drinks, cigarettes. Damage can be acute - a single burn from hot milk or broth, or chronic - the habit of drinking almost boiling coffee or tea, or exposure to hot smoke while smoking. The main areas of damage are the lips, the tip of the tongue and the hard palate. Hyperemia and edema appear. And with severe damage, blisters are formed, which burst immediately, as in the case of the moist environment of the oral cavity. In the mouth, you can see reddened areas of the mucous membrane with white epithelial pieces along the edges.

In the most severe lesions, necrotic (dead) tissue is observed, their color is gray or dark brown.

Research methods. For solving the set tasks and achieving the goal, medical and social, clinical and laboratory, functional and statistical methods of research were applied.

Object of the study. 290 patients (220 in the main groups and 60 in the control groups), aged 40-80 years, with the percentage of men and women 65.5% and 34.5%, respectively, were examined.

The objects of the study are patients with major dental diseases (carious lesions, periodontal diseases, lesions of the oral mucosa) in the presence (main groups) and absence (control groups) of chronic forms of coronary heart disease.

Practical significance:

To improve the effectiveness of treatment of major dental diseases in patients with chronic IBS, to evaluate the effectiveness of treatment of chronic IBS in the presence of basic dental

diseases in patients, practical recommendations on prevention, peculiarities of dental treatment and assessment of its effectiveness in patients with chronic forms of IBS are created. A comprehensive program of prevention and treatment of major dental diseases in patients with chronic forms of IBS is developed.

The treatment of such changes of OM provides elimination of circulatory insufficiency in combination with local symptomatic therapy. Oral cavity sanitation is performed, treatment with antiseptic and anesthetic solutions is prescribed. Trophic ulcers should be cleaned from necrotized tissues with enzyme preparations and prescribe means that accelerate epithelialization: propocium, extericide, solcoseryl, spedian, tsigerol, sea buckthorn oil, rosehip oil, oil solutions of vitamins A and E, inside drugs that normalize the state of the vascular wall and metabolic disorders: rutin, vitamins P and C, potassium orotate, riboxin, carnitine chloride and others, with means of oral hygiene in traumatic lesions, oral hygiene products for traumatic lesions.

Antibacterial and oxygen-containing foams. If there is severe pain in the damaged mucous membrane, it is impossible to brush the teeth. In this case, antibacterial foams will help. For example, foams from the Splat line with different flavors not only effectively remove plaque, but also help the oral cavity heal faster. Bloom oxygen spray is designed to care for damaged and inflamed gums. The active oxygen product is easy to use and does not stain tooth enamel, fillings and crowns.

Toothpastes. In order to prevent the development of complications during the treatment of damaged lesions, it is important to choose a paste that has an antibacterial effect. For example, Splat Special Zero Balance paste contains well over 99% natural ingredients. Buccotherm paste is suitable for pain and sensitivity of damaged gums. For prosthetic stomatitis, you can choose ROCS PRO moisturizing paste. This moisturizing paste helps fight dry mouth due to its ability to form a moisture-retaining layer in the mouth through the combination of potassium alginate and xylitol.

Toothbrushes. If the lesions of the oral mucosa are not severe and you can use a toothbrush, you should choose very soft options. Single beam brushes are suitable for injuries. They clean only the surfaces of the teeth without disturbing the gums.

Detergents. For traumatic injuries, especially burns, it is important to use rinses without strong antiseptics. You should pay attention to products from the Viscid line. Rinsing has an analgesic, restorative and anti-inflammatory effect. Zinc, which is part of it, helps to quickly restore taste sensitivity (in case of tongue burns) and accelerates the process of cell regeneration.

Gel Fagodent. Antibacterial gel is used to reduce the risk of bacterial infection and the development of ulcers. The composition contains only bacteriophages that fight against pathogenic microflora, while helping to restore the natural balance of oral microflora. For damage to the mucous membrane, Fagodent should be used several times a day, after each meal.

Diet - for damage to the mucous membrane of the oral cavity. The main rule of the diet is to maintain the usual calorie intake while changing the form of food.

During the healing period of the mucous membrane, try to eat only liquid and soft foods - mashed soups, porridges, mousses. Temporarily give up spices and reduce the amount of salt consumed. In addition to further irritating the damaged tissues, salt reduces the rate of cell renewal. Avoid juices and carbonated drinks. Fruit acids have a negative effect on damaged mucous membranes. In traumatic injuries, the most important thing is to eliminate the factor that caused the injury. Only after that, the process of restoring the mucous membrane begins. Preventive measures include giving up bad habits such as biting the mucous membrane, contacting a dentist

immediately if there is discomfort in the oral cavity, using a protective candle for braces during orthodontic treatment, trying not to eat very hot food and drinks.

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